

APPLICATION OF THE PROBABILISTIC METHOD TO PROPAGATE INPUT UNCERTAINTY ON A DBA SEQUENCE IN A GENERIC iPWR

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ABSTRACT

In view of the possible licensing needs of Small Modular Reactors (SMRs), the international scientific community is focusing on investigating the applicability of Severe Accident (SA) integral codes in simulating SMR response during postulated transients. Among the SMRs designs, the integral Pressurized Water Reactor (iPWR) concept, starting from the well-proven and established large Light Water Reactor (LWR) technology, is characterized by the adoption of passive safety systems and integral configuration. Within this framework, the Horizon Project “Safety Analysis of SMR with Passive Mitigation strategies – Severe Accident” (SASPAM – SA), coordinated by ENEA (Italy), is focused on investigating the applicability and transfer of operating large LWR knowledge and know-how to iPWRs in view of SA and Emergency Planning Zone (EPZ) European licensing needs. In this framework, the present study aims to provide initial insights on the application of Best Estimate Plus Uncertainty (BEPU) approach to SMR and about MECOR code uncertainties on the main thermal-hydraulic phenomena occurring in a generic iPWR..

KEYWORDS

SASPAM-SA; SMR; MELCOR; BEPU

1. INTRODUCTION

Computational integral Severe Accident (SA) codes, such as ASTEC [1] and MELCOR [2] [3], are developed to simulate the response of a Nuclear Power Plant (NPP) during mitigated and unmitigated scenarios and assess their safety. Nowadays, the international nuclear community involved in SAs is focused on investigating the applicability SA codes to light water Small Modular Reactors (SMRs), particular regarding on integral Pressurized Water Reactors (iPWRs). This SMR concept starts from the well-proven and tested Light Water Reactor (LWR) technology, incorporating operational plant experience and feedback as well as moderate evolutionary design modification to increase the inherent safety of the plant. Some of them are characterized by the adoption of an integral Reactor Pressure Vessel (RPV) containing all the Reactor Coolant System (RCS) components and the use of passive safety systems. In view of their licensing

process, state-of-the-art SA codes should be capable to simulate their advanced features and related phenomenology¹. Within this framework, the Horizon Euratom SASPAM-SA project [4], coordinated by ENEA (Italy), aims to assess the capability of internationally recognized European and Non-European computational tools (largely used in Europe)² to describe the behavior of the most promising iPWR designs during SA scenarios and predict radiological impact on- and off-site. Thermal-hydraulic characterization during nominal and transient condition represent a crucial point since the phenomena that characterize them are specific to the design, phenomena related to new system components or reactor configuration³ [5]. In this view, goal of the present work is to have a first insight about the uncertainties of the code, in terms of Figures Of Merit (FOM), on the thermal-hydraulic phenomena during a Design Basis Accident (DBA) scenario adopting a Best Estimate Plus Uncertainty (BEPU) approach [6]. Considering the iPWR mean features, a generic International Reactor Innovative and Secure (IRIS) [7] SMR type has been considered as reference to develop the MELCOR nodalization without using proprietary data but scaling the available data of the SPES-3 experimental facility [8] [9] as well as by engineering evaluation from public general data available. The probabilistic method to propagate input uncertainty [10] has been adopted to perform the uncertainty quantification analysis of a postulated Loss Of Coolant Accident (LOCA). Uncertain input parameters related to initial and boundary conditions and operation of passive safety systems have been selected based on literature and engineering judgment.

¹ Advanced designs, as iPWRs, are in general characterized by common features with the current operating large-LWR and by other specific features typical of their inherent evolutionary designs, providing safety advantages that reinforce the first three levels of the DiD principle. However, even if a plant is designed with advanced inherent features (through the reinforcement of the 1,2,3 DiD levels) allowing a reduction of the Core Damage Frequency (CDF), independent features for preventing and mitigating a severe accident sequence have to be included in its design (DiD level 4) together with the offsite emergency response (DiD level 5). Therefore, some scenarios that could lead to severe accidents need to be postulated and deterministically studied (More detailed information's in [30]). Therefore, it is necessary to assess the capability of internationally recognized SA code to describe the behaviour of the most promising iPWR designs during SA scenarios and to predict the resulting radiological impact on- and off-site.

² In order to maximize the knowledge transferability and impacts of the project two generic design-concepts, characterized by different evolutionary innovations in comparison with larger operating reactor, have been selected for the analyses: a) IPWR characterized by a submerged containment and electric power of about 60 MWe, called design 1; b) IPWR characterized by the use of several passive systems, a dry containment and an electric power of about 300 MWe, called design 2. These two generic reactor concepts include the main iPWR design features, considered in the most promising designs ready to go on the European market, allowing to assess in a wider way the capability of codes (SA and CFD) to simulate the SA phenomena typical of iPWR. It is not the project's objective to assess the generic reactor designs selected but, based on the project findings, allow a more general statement on the code's applicability to currently favored designs under postulated SA condition. No PSA considerations will be done in the project due to the generic nature of the reactor concept considered, then the scenarios identified will be characterized in terms of severity but not in terms of probability.

³ Passive systems are, on the one hand, an advanced solution to increase the inherent safety of the plant (e.g., there is no need of pumps), on the other hand a) they require extensive investigation for assessing the functional failure related to the thermal-hydraulic phenomena driving the operation of the systems and assess the related uncertainties, b) may still need an active initiation, and c) are characterized by very limited operational experience (to have more detailed information [30] [31]). Considering this, the impact of the operation of passive systems on postulated severe accident progression is a novel topic and needs to be assessed. Considering this, the specific assessment of the code capability to simulate passive systems phenomenology is crucial. Infact, in LW-SMR reactors the BDBA/SA scenarios evolution depend from the postulated partial or total not operation of passive systems (e.g. postulate the failure of passive system valve activation). Therefore, it is necessary to analyse the capability of SA codes to predict the main thermal-hydraulic phenomena involved in the passive mitigation strategy of LW-SMR in order to adequately apply them for the design of accident management's strategy (first phase of a SA is only dominated by T-H phenomena, then in-vessel is affected by thermal-hydraulic phenomena).

2. GENERIC iPWR DESIGN AND MELCOR INPUT-DECK DESCRIPTION

The design here studied is characterized by a dry spherical containment and the use of different passive systems, arranged in two parallel trains and features an integral RPV containing all the RCS components such as the Pressurizer (PRZ), a compact Steam Generators (SGs) (with the adoption of helical-coil tubes) and the Reactor Coolant Pumps (RCPs). The RPV is contained in the containment composed by the Drywell (DW) and the Reactor Cavity (RC). The iPWR passive mitigation strategy is based on several passive systems, which carry out different safety functions: *natural circulation in the RPV* (Riser-Downcomer -RIDC-), *decay heat removal* (Emergency Heat Removal System -EHRS-), *primary automatic depressurization* (Automatic Depressurization System -ADS-), *high pressure safety injection* (Emergency Boration Tanks -EBTs-), *low pressure safety injection* (Long-term Gravity Make-up System -LGMS-), *containment pressure suppression* (Pressure Suppression System -PSS- tanks), *flooding of the RC*. Except the heat sink of the decay heat removal system, all the passive systems considered in the passive mitigation strategy are supposed to be placed within the DW. A generic scheme of the iPWR layout, with the considered safety functions, is presented in Figure 1 [11].

Figure 1 Scheme of the generic iPWR design with the passive safety systems [11].

MELCOR [2] [3] is a fully integrated SA code able to simulate the thermal-hydraulic phenomena in steady and transient condition and the main SA phenomena characterizing the RPV, the RC, the containment, and the confinement buildings typical of LWR. The code, which presents a modular architecture, can be used with the Symbolic Nuclear Analysis Package (SNAP) [12]. The generic iPWR MELCOR nodalization, shown in Figure 2, developed in the framework of the SASPAM-SA project using MELCOR code version v2023, combines a trade-off between the computational time and a detailed prediction capability of the transient thermal-hydraulic and core degradation phenomenology. The two passive systems cooling lines, adopted by the selected design, have been modelled separately. The RPV has been modelled in different hydraulic CVH Control Volumes (CVs), coupled with FL flow path and HS, including the Lower Plenum (LP), the reactor core, the core by-pass, the riser, the Upper Plenum (UP), the SGs and the downcomer. To simplify the model, the eight SGs have been modelled as an equivalent one, with four CVH CVs on the primary side and eight CVs on the secondary side. The reactor core has been modelled by a single CV coupled with the correspondent COR package nodalization, characterized by sixteen axial levels and six

radial rings. The containment region has been modelled with one CVH CV for the DW region, as shown previously in Figure 2, thermally coupled with the CV representing the environment, and one CV for the RC, coupled with the CAV MELCOR package.

Figure 2 SNAP view of the MELCOR CVH and FL nodalization.

3. REFERENCE CASE

A LOCA accident, initiated by the double-ended guillotine break of one of the two DVI lines, has been considered as reference scenario [8] [11] [13] [14]. In general the transient starts with the break and the consequent RPV depressurization and containment pressurization. Once the containment high-pressure set-point is achieved, the S-Signal initiates the reactor SCRAM; due to this the isolation of the secondary side of SGs and the opening of two of the four EHRH loops occur⁴. A natural circulation in the EHRH system begins, permitting the transfer of the thermal power to the water inside the RWST tanks, the cooling of the RPV and its depressurization. The low level of the coolant in the PRZ triggers the RCPs coast-down and the following automatic opening of the RI-DC check valves. The LM-Signal (LOCA Mitigation) is then triggered when the PRZ pressure reaches the low pressure set-point. It determines the opening of the ADS stage-1, the start of the injection by EBTs and the opening of the two remaining EHRH system loops. At the primary and DW pressure equalization, the low RPV-DW differential pressure signal activates the LGMSs. Because of the steam condensation in the DW and the heat removed due to the EHRH system, the pressure in the DW decreases below the PSSs pressure. Consequently, the water inside the PSSs is forced upward through the PSS vent pipes, until filling the RC after dropping from the top end of the PSS vent pipe. This water head inside the PSS vent-pipe maintains a differential pressure between the LGMS (equal to PSS) and RPV (equal to DW) throughout the depressurization phase, which improves the LGMS water injection. Steam circulation between RPV and DW is enabled by the ADS stage-2 valves opening upon reaching the LGMS low water mass signal. The water in the RC keeps the core filled during the long-term cooling phase. The heat losses through the DW metal walls to the environment and the power extracted by the EHRH systems allow the cooling down of the core. The MELCOR simulation of the reference calculation has been performed considering an initial steady-state analysis of 2000 s to reach systems nominal conditions. Comparing the steady-state results with reference values [7], a discrepancy less than 3% has been evaluated.

⁴ For the analyses presented in the paper, because of the nodalizations structure (only one equivalent EHRH), the logic is simplified and only one actuation of EHRH is considered.

The Start Of the Transient (SOT) has been considered at $t=0$ s with the opening of the break and the calculation has been performed for 50000 s. Table 1 reports the main phenomena characterizing the transient and predicted by MELCOR with their timings.

Table 1 Main events characterizing the MELCOR reference case.

Event	Time [s]
Break	0
High Containment pressure signal (SCRAM, isolation SG, EHRS activation)	41
Low PRZ water level signal (Pump coast down and RI-DC opening)	122
Low PRZ pressure signal (ADS Stage-1 opening, EBTs opening)	148
Low DP RV-Containment (LGMSs opening)	1884
1st RPV- DW pressure equalization	2000
2nd RPV- DW pressure equalization	3315
1st vent injection	3010
2nd vent injection	5405
Core level reach the TAF	3000
Cavity level reach the DVI	3950
Low LGMS mass (ADS Stage -2 opening)	12265

4. UNCERTAINTY QUANTIFICATION METHODOLOGY AND COMPUTATIONAL ENVIRONMENT

Among the uncertainty methodologies developed in the past to conduct uncertainty quantification analyses [6], the probabilistic method to propagate input uncertainty [10] is based, in general, on statistical approaches to correlate the input uncertainty, identified by the uncertain input parameters, to output uncertainty, expressed in the uncertainty of selected FOMs. Each uncertain input parameter is identified by a Probability Density Function (PDF), usually selected based on previous analyses, available experimental data, and engineering judgment [15]. A Monte Carlo random sampling of the uncertain input parameters is performed to define a number N of sets of values of the uncertain input parameters used to defined N input-deck used to start N code runs. The Wilks's formula [16] [17] can be used to determine the minimum number of code runs N based on the requested probability content γ and confidence level β . If multiple FOMs p are analysed, N is calculated using the Wald's formula [18], presented below for the *one-sided tolerance interval*:

$$\beta = \sum_{j=0}^{N-p} \binom{N}{j} \alpha^j (1 - \alpha)^{N-j} \quad (1)$$

More details on the statistical aspects can be found in [19]. As well as assessing the uncertainty width of FOMs, the *mean*, *median*, *standard deviation* and *coefficient of variation* are calculated in this work. To have insights about the statistical correlation between the FOMs and the selected uncertain input parameters the *simple* and *simple rank correlation coefficients* are computed [20] [21] [22] [23].

The Uncertainty Tool (UT) used in this uncertainty application, shown in Figure 3, can perform all the steps needed for the development of an uncertainty analysis [24]. This tool has been developed and applied along the H2020 MUSA project, coordinated by CIEMAT(Spain) [29]. The user specifies the N number of code runs desired as well as the uncertainty parameters selected for analysis and the tool, by the sampling, creates the N sets of parameters to be replaced in an input-deck template. After executing the code runs, the tool manages the FOMs calculated data extraction by using the AptBatch executable [25] and, then, develops the statistical analysis of the results and the post-processing.

Figure 3 Workflow of the uncertainty in-house UT used with MELCOR code in a Python environment/architecture.

5. UNCERTAINTY ANALYSIS OF THE DBA SEQUENCE

Goal of the present study is not to be a comprehensive uncertainty study from the uncertain input parameters used and FOMs selected view but to develop of a full uncertainty analysis on iPWR design using the probabilistic method to propagate input uncertainty as well as to give some insights about the statistical correlation between uncertain input parameters and the FOMs. Following as done in [20], the FOMs selected for the present analysis are: peak of maximum cladding temperature (referred to as FOM_1), minimum collapsed coolant level in the core region (referred to as FOM_2) and the maximum containment pressure (referred to as FOM_3). The uncertain input parameters, listed in Table 2 have been selected and extrapolated from [26] [27] [28] and based on engineering judgment. Considering equation (1), 129 code runs are needed considering a probability γ and confidence level β of 95%. For the present application, the failed runs have not been considered and have been replaced with new ones with a different combination of the uncertain input parameters, adopting the approach mentioned in [29]. In Table 3, based on the analyses, the main statistical parameters characterizing the FOMs have been shown. A mean value of 504.74 K and an uncertainty width of 42.77 K has been estimated for FOM_1, with a standard deviation of 8.23 K. The FOM_2 is characterized by a mean value of 4.46 m with an uncertainty band of 0.7m and standard deviation of 0.16 m; The FOM_3 is characterized by a mean value of 11.37E5 Pa, with an uncertainty width of 3.76E5 Pa and a standard deviation of 0.82E5 Pa. The empirical PDFs of the FOMs have been calculated as well as the simple and simple rank correlation coefficients by means the Pearson and Spearman's correlations for each FOM and uncertain input parameters. From the statistical correlation analysis, the parameters with a significant or moderate statistical correlations with the FOM_1 are the Heat Transfer Surface of EHRS HXs (negative correlation) and the ADS Stage-1 loss coefficient (positive correlation). Regarding the FOM_2, a moderate statistical correlation with the initial DW pressure (positive correlation) and Heat Transfer Surface of EHRS HXs (negative correlation) has been underlined. A significant statistical correlation with ADS Stage-1 loss coefficient has been evaluated (positive correlation). The FOM_3 presents a moderate statistical correlation (positive correlation) with the initial DW pressure (as expected) and a significant statistical correlation with the ADS Stage-1 loss coefficient (negative correlation). From Figure 4 to Figure 9 the estimated PDF of the FOMs and the scatter plot of these parameters are shown.

Table 2 Uncertain input parameters.

Uncertain input parameter	Unit	PDF	Reference value	Lower and upper bound		Reference
				Min	Max	
Decay Power	[-] (multiplier)	Normal	1.0	Min	0.98	[27]
				Max	1.02	
Initial PRZ pressure	[Pa]	Normal	1.55E7	Min	1.54E7	[27]
				Max	1.56E7	
EBT initial temperature	[K]	Normal	321.9	Min	311.9	[27]
				Max	331.9	
LGMS initial temperature	[K]	Normal	321.9	Min	311.9	[27]
				Max	331.9	
Initial DW pressure	[Pa]	Uniform	1.013E5	Min	0.85E5	[27]
				Max	1.15E5	
RWST initial liquid level	[m]	Normal	9.0	Min	8.9390	[26]
				Max	9.0610	
RWST and environment initial temperature	[K]	Uniform	293.0	Min	283.0	[28]
				Max	303.0	
Heat Transfer Surface EHRs HXs	[-] (multiplier)	Uniform	1.0	Min	0.75	[26]
				Max	1.25	
Break Flow discharge coefficient	[-]	Uniform	0.7	Min	0.7	Engineering Judgement
				Max	1.0	
EHRs valves loss coefficient	[%]	Uniform	0	Min	-100	Engineering Judgement
				Max	+100	
EBT valves loss coefficient	[%]	Uniform	0	Min	-100	Engineering Judgement
				Max	+100	
LGMS valve loss coefficient	[%]	Uniform	0	Min	-100	Engineering Judgement
				Max	+100	
ADS Stage-1 loss coefficient	[%]	Uniform	0	Min	-100	Engineering Judgement
				Max	+100	
ADS Stage-2 loss coefficient	[%]	Uniform	0	Min	-100	Engineering Judgement
				Max	+100	

Table 3 Statistical parameters of the FOMs.

Statistical parameter	FOM_1		FOM_2		FOM_3	
	Value	Unit	Value	Unit	Value	Unit
Mean	504.74	[K]	4.46	[m]	11.37E5	[Pa]
Median	505.53	[K]	4.47	[m]	11.32E5	[Pa]
Lower Bound	483.66	[K]	4.05	[m]	9.73E5	[Pa]
Upper Bound	526.43	[K]	4.75	[m]	13.49E5	[Pa]
Standard deviation	8.23	[K]	0.16	[m]	0.82E5	[Pa]
Coefficient of variation	0.016	[-]	0.037	[-]	0.072	[-]

To characterize the uncertainty width of the code's results during throughout the transient, the values of the N cases referred to the maximum cladding temperature, core collapsed coolant level and DW pressure have been compared at each time-step to the reference case and the mean, median, upper and lower bound.

Figure 4 Empirical PDF of the FOM_1.

Figure 5 Scatter plot of FOM_1.

Figure 6 Empirical PDF of the FOM_2.

Figure 7 Scatter plot of FOM_2.

Figure 8 Empirical PDF of the FOM_3.

Figure 9 Scatter plots of FOM_3.

In addition, the trend of the simple correlation coefficient during the first 10000 s of the transient have been considered with respect to the uncertain input parameters previously mentioned. The maximum cladding temperature, shown in Figure 10 presents an uncertainty width of about 25 K during the first 1000 s after the SOT. Then, it increases reaching an amplitude of about 100 K, between 1000 and 2000 s. In this time region, come code runs present a peak up to 525 K. After that, the uncertainty width remains almost constant and equal to about 25 K. As highlighted in Figure 11, regarding the initial DW pressure and Heat Transfer Surface of EHRS HXs parameters, the magnitude of the correlation increases from low to moderate or significant along the transient, while the magnitude of the correlation for the ADS Stage-1 loss coefficient

parameter goes from significant to moderate along the long-term phase. The uncertainty width of the core collapsed coolant level, shown in Figure 12⁵, increases its amplitude after 200 s of the SOT to a value of 1.20 m and reach its maximum value at about 3000 s after the SOT. As can be seen from Figure 12 the attainment of the TAF during the transient has a very high uncertainty width in time terms, reaching an uncertainty width of about 4000 seconds. As shown in Figure 13, the ADS-1 loss coefficient has a statistically significant correlation for the first 4000 s of the transient.

Figure 10 Uncertainty band of the maximum cladding temperature.

Figure 11 Simple correlation coefficient referred for the maximum cladding temperature.

Figure 12 Uncertainty band of the core collapsed coolant level.

Figure 13 Simple correlation coefficient for the core collapsed coolant level.

The heat transfer surface of the EHRS HXs has a significant correlation (positive correlation) after about 4000 s. The initial pressure of the DW presents a moderate statistical correlation after about 1000 seconds after the SOT. The uncertainty width of the DW pressure, shown in Figure 14, presents a maximum value of the band at about 3000 s after the SOT and equal to about 7E5 Pa. The pressure of the DW is characterized by a statistically significant correlation with its initial value (as expected) in the first instants of the transient, and at about 1000 s from the SOT, as highlighted in Figure 15. The ADS-1 loss coefficient is also a parameter

⁵ With reference to the **Error! Reference source not found.**, the uncertainty width is cut just above the TAF as only the volume representative of this region has been considered for the collapsed level.

with a significant correlation, which in the first 1000 s shows a significant statistical correlation of a negative type and then of a positive type. After the reflow phase, the heat transfer surface of the EHRS HXs shows a statistically significant negative correlation.

Figure 14 Uncertainty band of the FOM_3.

Figure 15 Simple correlation coefficient for the DW pressure.

6. CONCLUSIONS

The present work presented the uncertainty analysis of a DBA sequence in a generic iPWR. The activity has been performed, following a BEPU application, using the SA integral code MELCOR and an in-house UT developed in a Python environment/architecture. Aim of the work is to apply the probabilistic method to propagate input uncertainty in view to have some insight about the code uncertainties on the main thermal-hydraulic phenomena characterizing a mitigated transient in such scenario. Three relevant FOMs in term of plant safety and fourteen uncertain input parameters related to initial and boundary conditions and on passive safety system have been considered. The analysis gives first insights into the uncertainties of the code concerning the key TH phenomena during a mitigated transient scenario. In addition, by calculating the statistical correlation coefficients, it has been possible to identify the input uncertainty parameters with a moderate or significant statistical correlation with the FOMs. In this regard, a moderate or significant statistical correlation between FOMs and the Heat Transfer Surface of EHRS HXs, the initial pressure in the DW and the ADS-1 loss coefficient has been underlined. This study not only support but also extend the current activity done in SASPAM-SA consisting in assessing the capability of internationally recognized computational tools (largely used in Europe) to describe the behaviour of the most promising iPWR designs during mitigated and unmitigated scenarios. The next step will be to extend the uncertainty analyses to a postulated SA scenarios in order to identify the parameters that have a moderate/significant statistical correlation with SA FOMs.

NOMENCLATURE

ADS: Automatic Depressurization System; **BEPU:** Best Estimate Plus Uncertainty; **DBA:** Design Basis Accident; **DVI:** Direct Vessel Injection; **DW:** Drywell; **EBT:** Emergency Boration Tank; **EHRS:** Emergency Heat Removal System; **EPZ:** Emergency Planning Zone; **FOM:** Figure Of Merit; **HX:** Heat eXchanger; **iPWR:** Integral Pressurized Water Reactor; **IRIS:** International Reactor Innovative and Secure; **LGMS:** Long Term Gravity Make-up System; **LOCA:** Loss Of Coolant Accident; **LP:** Lower Plenum; **LWR:** Light Water Reactor; **NPP:** Nuclear Power Plant; **PDF:** Probability Density Function; **PRZ:** Pressurizer; **PSS:** Pressure Suppression System; **QT:** Quench Tank; **RC:** Reactor Cavity; **RCP:** Reactor Coolant Pump; **RCS:** Reactor Coolant System; **RPV:** Reactor Pressure Vessel; **RWST:** Refueling Water

Storage Tank; **SA**: Severe Accident; **SG**: Steam Generator; **SMR**: Small Modular Reactor; **SNAP**: Symbolic Nuclear Analysis Package; **SOT**: Start Of the Transient; **UP**: Upper Plenum; **UT**: Uncertainty Tool.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS & DISCLAIMER

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Commission-Euratom. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

UNIPA carried out the research activity with MELCOR code and SNAP, obtained in the framework of the UNIPA-ISIN agreement signed on March 26th 2021 as part of the General Arrangement between the United States Nuclear Regulatory Commission (US-NRC) and the Italian National Inspectorate for Nuclear Safety and Radiation Protection (ISIN).

ENEA carried out the research activity with MELCOR code and SNAP, obtained in the framework of the UNIPA-ISIN agreement signed on March 23th 2020 as part of the General Arrangement between the United States Nuclear Regulatory Commission (US-NRC) and the Italian National Inspectorate for Nuclear Safety and Radiation Protection (ISIN).

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